

The Relationship of Social Support on Stress Levels in Final Level Students at the Faculty of Teaching and Educational Sciences, Islamic University of Riau

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Abstract:- Social support affects health by protecting individuals against the negative effects of severe stress. People with good social support have a tendency not to ignore stress because they know they will get help from others and vice versa, with social support that is not good it will exacerbate the stress they experience. This study aims to determine the relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teaching and Education, Islamic University of Riau. This type of research is quantitative with the research design being correlation. The population in this study was 120 final year students, and the sample taken was 114 respondents. Research using a questionnaire. The data obtained was processed using univariate and bivariate analysis. The results of the study obtained a P Value of 0.014 meaning a P Value <0.05, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teaching and Education, Islamic University of Riau. Suggestion: Final year students are expected to be able to manage the stress they experience in order to prevent stress.

Keywords:- Social support, stress level, final year students.

I. INTRODUCTION

A student is someone who is in the process of gaining knowledge or studying and is registered as undergoing education at one of the forms of tertiary institutions consisting of academics, polytechnics, high schools, institutes and universities (Hartaji, 2012). In the Indonesian Dictionary (KBI), students are defined as individuals studying at tertiary institutions (KBBI, 2011).

Students are students who are registered at the higher education institution level, where their most important task is that they are required to have independence and responsibility to complete the academic tasks that have been set, in order to achieve the graduation competencies expected by their alma mater. Student academic tasks include coursework that must be completed on time, achievement of study load, practicums, Field Work Practices (PKL) and final assignments. However, in the process of completing their academic assignments, students will be faced with various obstacles. These obstacles will increase as the level of education one reaches. Likewise with final year students, where at this level students are faced with stressors in order to complete their studies.

(Ushfuriyah, 2015).

According to Syofia (quoted from Zakiyah, 2016) said that the many stressors and demands faced by students can be a particular pressure for students, causing stress to arise due to preparing their final assignments. Research conducted by Iswanto (2014) with respondents of 72 students who were preparing their final assignments, showed that 15.3% of students experienced severe stress, 41.7% of students experienced moderate stress and 43.0% of students experienced mild stress.

According to Hans Selye (quoted from Hidayat, 2013) stress is a non-specific body response to any disturbed bodily needs, a universal phenomenon that occurs in everyday life and cannot be avoided by everyone, stress has a total impact on the individual, namely physical, psychological, intellectual, social and spiritual, stress can threaten physiological balance. One factor that can change an individual's perception of stressful events and can reduce the potential for stress is social support (Maslihah, 2011). According to Gottlieb (quoted from Syafitri, 2015) social support consists of verbal and non-verbal information or advice, real help or actions provided by social familiarity or obtained because of the presence of supportive people.

According to Videback (quoted from Nurdianti, 2017) individuals who receive emotional and functional support are proven to be healthier compared to individuals who do not receive support. In line with the results of research by Mulyani (2012) with a sample of 25 students regarding the relationship between social support and the stress level of final year students in completing their final assignments, it was found that there was a negative relationship between social support and psychological reactions to the stress of students who were working on their final assignments.

According to McGinley (quoted from Nurdianti, 2017) social support functions as a buffer against stress by preventing situations that are considered stressors by providing solutions to alleviate problems thereby minimizing the stress felt. Adjustment to the effects of stress depends on the availability of external (including social support) and internal (a person's use of coping strategies) support.

In Indonesia, mental disorders are still a significant problem. Riskesdas 2013 stated that the prevalence of emotional mental disorders in Indonesia reached 14 million people or 6% of the total population in Indonesia aged 15 years and over. Based on the results of the 2013 Basic Health Research Survey (Riskesdas) dimensioned by the Basic Health Research and Development Agency (Balitbangkes), it shows that the highest prevalence of severe stress occurs in the Yogyakarta Special Region Province, showing that around 3 out of every 1000 final year students experience severe stress (Riskesdas, 2013).

According to research by (Dagnew & Dagne, 2019) conducted at the University of Gondar in Ethiopia, the prevalence of emotional mental disorders in students was 40.9%, while according to research conducted at German University the prevalence of emotional mental disorders in students was 22.7% (Rahmayani., et al, 2017). Similar research has also been carried out in several countries in Asia, one of which is in public and private medical schools in Bangladesh with 1363 respondents stating that the prevalence of stress is 73%, of which 64% in men and 36% in women (Eva EO., et al, 2015). The results of this study are almost the same as research conducted at Jizan University, it was found that the prevalence of stress in medical students was 71.9%. The prevalence of stress in women is 77%, while men are lower, namely 64% (Sani, 2012).

In research (Lestari, 2017) it is known that students experience stress due to lack of attention, appreciation, concern, input and suggestions as well as information and instructions to carry out lectures well, whether from family, friends and lecturers. Final year students feel stressed and burdened due to busy study schedules, piling up coursework, feeling tense when faced with problems, and some even feel like they have lost their enthusiasm for studying because their expectations do not match their plans. Several related studies regarding the relationship between social support and stress levels, namely according to Suci Lestari in 2017, D IV Midwife Educator Study Program, Faculty of Health Sciences, 'Aisyiyah University, Yogyakarta, showed that 73 respondents, a total of 26 students (35.6%) were not stressed with social support. high, 2 students (2.7%) had no stress with moderate social support, 33 students (45.2%) had mild levels of stress with high social support, 2 students (2.7%) had mild levels of stress with mild social support, 6 students (8.2%) had a moderate level of stress with high social support, 1 student (1.4%) had a moderate level of stress with

moderate social support, 2 students (2.7%) had a high level of stress with social support moderate and 1 student (1.4%) has a high stress level with low social support.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

An initial survey conducted on several students showed that of the 15 people who underwent initial interviews, it was found that 9 people had poor social support, such as lacking/not receiving support in the form of motivation, empathy and goods. The results of interviews with 9 people who had poor social support found that 7 people experienced stress.

From this background description, researchers are interested in conducting further research on "The Relationship between Social Support and Stress Levels in Final Year Students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University in 2023".

The problem formulation in this research is "Is there a relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University in 2023?"

General Objectives To find out the relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University in 2023.

III. METHOD

In this study, researchers used a type of quantitative research that is correlational with a cross-sectional research design, which aims to obtain information about the relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teaching and Education, Islamic University of Riau in 2023 (Kundre, 2017). The population in this study was 120 final year students, and the sample taken was 114 respondents. Research using a questionnaire. The data obtained was processed using univariate and bivariate analysis.

IV. ANALYSIS

The results of distributing the online/google form questionnaire which was carried out on August 21, 2023 at the Teaching and Education Faculty of Riau Islamic University to 114 respondents about the relationship of social support to stress levels in final year students, the results are as follows:

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents based on social support

No.	Social Support	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Good	53	46.5
2	Not Good	61	53.5
Total		114	100

Based on table 1 above, it shows that of the 114 respondents at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University, the distribution of the

majority of respondents had poor social support, amounting to 61 respondents (53.5%) while good social support was 53 respondents (46.5%).

Table 2: Frequency distribution of respondents based on stress level

No.	Stress Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Light	17	14.9
2	Currently	71	62.3
4	Heavy	26	22.8
Total		114	100

Based on the table above, it shows that of the 114 respondents at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University, the distribution of respondents according to stress level, the majority were

moderate stress, amounting to 71 respondents (62.3%), while there were 17 respondents (14.9%) with mild stress.) and severe stress as many as 26 respondents (22.8%).

Table 3: The relationship between social support and stress levels

Social Support	Stress Level				P value
	Light	Currently	Heavy	Total	
Good	11	36	6	53	0.014
Not Good	6	35	20	61	
Total	17	71	26	114	

The results of the analysis of the relationship between social support and stress levels showed that 114 respondents, 11 respondents (9.6%) had mild stress with good social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) had mild stress with poor social support, 36 respondents (31.5%) moderate stress with good social support, 35 respondents (30.8%) moderate stress with poor social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) severe stress with good social support, 20 respondents (17.5%) severe stress with social support is not good. The statistical test results show that the P value = $0.014 < \alpha = 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University.

According to research by (Dagne & Dagne, 2019) conducted at the University of Gondar in Ethiopia, the prevalence of emotional mental disorders in students was 40.9%, while according to research conducted at German University the prevalence of emotional mental disorders in students was 22.7% (Rahmayani., et al, 2017). Similar studies have also been conducted in several countries in Asia, one of which was in public and private medical schools in Bangladesh with 1363 respondents stating that the prevalence of stress was 73%, of which 64% were in men and 36% in women (Eva EO., et al, 2015). The results of this study are almost the same as research conducted at Jizan University, it was found that the prevalence of stress in medical students was 71.9%. The prevalence of stress in women is 77%, while men are lower, namely 64% (Sani, 2012).

V. DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of the relationship between social support and stress levels showed that 114 respondents, 11 respondents (9.6%) had mild stress with good social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) had mild stress with bad social support, 36 respondents (31.5 %) moderate stress with good social support, 35 respondents (30.8%) moderate stress with bad social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) severe stress with good social support, 20 respondents (17.5%) severe stress with social support is not good. The statistical test results show that the P value = $0.014 < \alpha = 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teaching and Education, Riau Islamic University

In Lestari's research (2017), it is known that students experience stress due to lack of attention, appreciation, concern, input and suggestions as well as information and instructions to carry out lectures well, whether from family, friends and lecturers. Final year students feel stressed and burdened due to busy study schedules, piling up coursework, feeling tense when faced with problems, and some even feel like they have lost their enthusiasm for studying because their expectations do not match their plans.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Suci Lestari (2017) on 73 final year students that there are positive results between social support and stress levels.

Several related studies regarding the relationship between social support and stress levels, namely according to Suci Lestari in 2017, D IV Midwife Educator Study Program, Faculty of Health Sciences, 'Aisyiyah University, Yogyakarta, showed that 73 respondents, a total of 26 students (35.6%) were not stressed with social support. high, 2 students (2.7%) had no stress with moderate social support, 33 students (45.2%) had mild levels of stress with high social support, 2 students (2.7%) had mild levels of stress with mild social support , 6 students (8.2%) had a moderate level of stress with high social support, 1 student (1.4%) had a moderate level of stress with moderate social support, 2 students (2.7%) had a high level of stress with social support moderate and 1 student (1.4%) has a high stress level with low social support. According to the researcher's assumptions, the source of stress on students in

completing the final assignment is within themselves, generally due to conflicts that occur between different desires and reality. Given that humans are spiritual and physical beings, stressors can be divided into three, namely spiritual (spiritual) stressors, mental (psychological) stressors, and physical (physical) stressors. So social support plays a very important role in managing stress in students in completing their final assignments. Family, community and environmental support are also sources of stress. Lack of interpersonal relationships, as well as lack of recognition in society, are causes of stress in the environment and society.

VI. CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis of the relationship between social support and stress levels showed that 114 respondents, 11 respondents (9.6%) had mild stress with good social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) had mild stress with poor social support, 36 respondents (31.5%) moderate stress with good social support, 35 respondents (30.8%) moderate stress with poor social support, 6 respondents (5.3%) severe stress with good social support, 20 respondents (17.5%) severe stress with social support is not good. The statistical test results show that the P value = $0.014 < \alpha = 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between social support and stress levels in final year students at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau Islamic University.

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